

EDUCATIONAL REFORMS IN THE NEW UZBEKISTAN AND THEIR RESULTS AS AN EXAMPLE OF TSPU

Gabdulmanova Ilnura

Master of the 2nd course of direction "Music education and art"
TSPU named after Nizami

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7298583>

Abstract: This article discusses the reforms implemented in the field of education today and their results.

Key words: Education system, reform, Law on Education, Higher education, international relations.

Today, all spheres of the life of New Uzbekistan have become a field of deep reforms. In this process, it is impossible not to talk excitedly about the changes in the educational system, which is considered the basis of the social sphere. In recent years, practical work on the organization of all stages of the education system based on modern requirements has entered a decisive stage in our country.

The need to modernize the entire system of teacher training at the university is associated with major changes that have taken place in the education system. The main task was to train a specialist with a high level of professional culture and competence, adequate to the new requirements for the quality of school education. The effectiveness of solving this problem depends on solving a whole range of problems and tasks of higher pedagogical education related to the search for new approaches to building a teacher training system at a university and improving its content.¹

Reforms in the higher education system constitute the main part of the reforms implemented in the field of education. In particular, to determine the priorities of the systematic reform of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, to raise the process of training independent thinking highly qualified personnel to a new level in terms of quality, to modernize higher education, based on advanced educational technologies In order to develop the social sector and economic sectors, the Concept of the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, approved by the decree of the head of our state on October 8, 2019, serves as a prelude to new reforms in the field.

This document was based on tasks such as the development of integration of science, education and production in order to accelerate intellectual development, train competitive personnel, effectively organize scientific and innovative activities, and strengthen international cooperation.

The content of the concept reflects the priorities of the reform of the higher education system of our country. It includes expanding the level of coverage and improving the quality of education in higher educational institutions, introducing digital technologies and educational platforms, attracting young people to scientific activities, forming innovative structures, commercializing the results of scientific research, achieving international recognition and

¹ Тригулова, А. Х. Предметная интеграция и ее значение в профессиональной подготовке будущего учителя музыки / А. Х. Тригулова // Молодой ученый. — 2018. — № 12 (198). — С. 173-175.

other improvements. Plab clearly defined directions. All this serves to raise the educational process to a new level of quality.

Today, it is no secret that the world's prestigious higher education institutions are considered to be the major hotbeds of science. Currently, new higher educational institutions and branches of the world's leading universities are being established. For example, in the last 5 years, 47 new higher educational institutions, including branches of foreign universities, were established in our country, and the number of higher educational institutions reached 125.

Non-governmental higher education institutions are being established on the basis of the public-private partnership system. Based on the opinion of the population, part-time and evening forms of education have been restored, admission quotas are being increased. The enrollment rate of school graduates in higher education increased from 9% in 2016 to 35% in 2020.

A mechanism has been created to ensure that professors-teachers can improve their skills and undergo internships in higher education and scientific-research institutions abroad. Their monthly salary was increased by an average of 2.5 times compared to 2018. Since this year, 10 higher education institutions have been transferred to the self-financing system.

The number of state grants allocated to higher education has been increased by at least 25%, the number of grants for girls from needy families for admission to higher education institutions has been doubled to 2,000, further expanding the scope of higher education coverage.

One of the most important innovations in the education system is the transfer of 65 academic lyceums to higher educational institutions, as well as 187 technical schools, in order to strengthen the cohesion between universities and lower levels of the education system. It was attached to related universities and branch enterprises.

In the process of developing science and innovation, turning their achievements into products with high added value, reliable protection of intellectual property is of particular importance. According to data, the share of intellectual property is 45 percent of the gross domestic product in Europe, 12 percent in China, and 7 percent in Russia. The meeting chaired by our President on October 12, 2020 was dedicated to the topic "Protection of intellectual property - serves as a reliable foundation for the Third Renaissance". At that time, the head of our state paid special attention to the need to ensure cooperation between patent owners and entrepreneurs.

In particular, one of the most important documents adopted in the education system was the adoption of the new version of the Law "On Education". Based on this law, the main principles, educational system, types and forms in the field of education were clearly defined.

Also, according to the law, state higher education, secondary specialized, professional educational institutions and their branches, higher, secondary specialized, professional educational organizations with state participation and their branches are organized by the decisions of the President or the government. it was done. Establishment of non-state educational institutions was determined to be carried out by their founders. The license to non-state educational organizations will be issued by the State Inspectorate for Quality Control of Education.

Accordingly, we can say that the adoption and implementation of this Law was one of the most important documents adopted in the field of education.

The reforms implemented in the field of education in Uzbekistan in recent years are consistently implemented at the Tashkent State Pedagogical University. As a result of these reforms, international relations should be emphasized. According to the memorandum signed with Saitnazar Saidi State Pedagogical Institute of Turkmenistan and the proposal of the Ministry of Education of the Republic of Turkmenistan, Rector of Nizomi Tashkent State Pedagogical University A. Kyrgyzbayev and Vice-Rector for International Cooperation acting O. Ismailov took part in the international conference on "Education, health care, sports" held in Ashgabat on October 10-11.

At the main plenary session of this international conference, the lecture of the rector of our university on the topic "Prospects for the development of higher pedagogical education in New Uzbekistan" was heard. A meeting was also organized with the Minister of Education of the Republic of Turkmenistan G. Atayeva. At this meeting, it was agreed on the cooperation of conferences, seminars, and the involvement of experienced professors of Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami for the students of Turkmen Pedagogical Institute named after Saidnazar Saidi.

In addition, a training session was held on the topic of "International economic cooperation" by the vice-rector for international cooperation of our university for the students of the Maktumkuli State University of Turkmenistan.

In addition, on October 27, at the Uzbekistan-Russia educational forum, an agreement was signed between Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami and Kalmykia State University of the Russian Federation. At the same time, a number of activities and plans for future cooperation were discussed. These mutual cooperations are the prelude to reforms in the new Uzbekistan education system.

On the initiative of the President, the granting of academic and organizational, as well as financial independence for higher education organizations and the expansion of the powers of the Councils are the implementation of the state policy in the field of education, the provision of quality education services and the fulfillment of the tasks assigned by our government in this regard. It creates ample opportunities for the training of potential personnel who determine the development of our country.

Today, modern life cannot be imagined without the progress of science and education, as if humanity revolves around the axis of science. It is not for nothing that the development of education in the leading countries of the world is defined as the first task. After all, the future development of the country is closely related to its achievements in this field.

Today, the educational activities of universities are further improved, and the quality of our people's desire for knowledge, which has been formed over the centuries, is once again being manifested. Our young people are trying to live a healthy and beautiful life, to have a permanent job in their profession, to take responsibility, not to belittle their human dignity, in short, to achieve perfection, and in this process they see education as the most important condition.

In short, all the conditions are being created for studying, learning, gaining knowledge, and now, in response to these initiatives put forward by our President, we, the youth, study more than ever and work harder on ourselves. Today's requirement is that we should become not only a support for our nation, our country, but also children, staff, specialists who will be confident in the future and determine the future.

I would like to quote the important words of the President in his address to the people. This is what it says in the petition. In order to raise the value of the title of teacher in the school system, to increase its moral and material support, and for this, to increase the monthly salary paid to them, in particular, for teaching staff who work from one district to another, they should receive a monthly salary. In the petition, the President emphasized that 50% of the salary, and 100% overtime if he goes to work in another region. At the end of my article, I would like to give an example that a person who has learned science never loses. After all, a person who loves and respects his people, his beloved country, and his loving parents will never stop worrying about tomorrow's future.

References:

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Education (National database of legal documents, 09/24/2020, No. 03/20/637/1313).
2. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility should be the daily rules of every leader's activity. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2017. - 46 p.
2. Тригулова, А. Х. Предметная интеграция и ее значение в профессиональной подготовке будущего учителя музыки / А. Х. Тригулова // Молодой ученый. — 2018. — № 12 (198). — С. 173-175.
1. www.wikipediya.uz
2. www.ziyo.net
3. <https://www.gazeta.uz/oz/2022/09/30/president/>
4. <https://new.tdpu.uz/news/8670>

